

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Study Title: Beyond Push–Pull: Emotional Ambivalence and Digital Networks in Nigerian Teachers' Migration Intentions

Invitation to Participate

You are being invited to take part in a research study conducted by a researcher in the field of education. This study explores how emotional experiences and digital professional networks influence Nigerian teachers' intentions to migrate or remain in their current teaching positions. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you are free to decide whether to take part.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine how emotional ambivalence (mixed feelings about career and migration) and engagement with digital professional networks influence Nigerian secondary school teachers' migration intentions. The study seeks to generate knowledge that may inform teacher retention strategies and professional development policies.

Why You Have Been Chosen

You have been selected to participate because you are a secondary school teacher with at least three years of teaching experience. Your professional experiences and perspectives are valuable to this study.

What Participation Involves

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to take part in a one-on-one interview. The interview will last approximately 45–60 minutes and may be conducted in person or online, depending on your preference and availability.

The interview will include questions about:

- Your professional experiences as a teacher
- Your engagement with digital professional networks
- Your thoughts and feelings about career mobility and migration

With your permission, the interview will be audio-recorded to ensure accurate transcription.

Voluntary Participation and Right to Withdraw

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may choose not to take part or withdraw from the study at any time without providing a reason. You may withdraw your participation up until the point where data analysis begins. After this stage, it may not be possible to remove your data because it will have been anonymised and integrated into the analysis.

Risks and Discomforts

There are no known significant risks associated with participating in this study. However, some questions may require you to reflect on your professional experiences and career decisions. You may skip any question you do not feel comfortable answering.

Benefits of Participation

There are no direct personal benefits to you for participating in this study. However, the findings may contribute to improving understanding of teacher migration, professional development, and education policy in Nigeria and similar contexts.

Confidentiality and Data Protection

All information you provide will be treated with strict confidentiality. Your identity will not appear in any reports, publications, or presentations arising from this study. Instead, pseudonyms or codes will be used.

All data will be:

- Stored securely on password-protected devices
- Accessible only to the research team
- Retained for a period of five years after publication and then securely deleted, in line with the University of Johannesburg's research data retention policy

Data Access

Anonymised excerpts of interview data may be shared with qualified researchers upon reasonable request and under a data access agreement.

This study follows the ethical research guidelines of the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) and the University of Johannesburg's data protection policies.

Contact Information

If you have any questions or concerns about this study, you may contact:

Principal Researcher: Chidubem Deborah Adamu

Email: cadamu@uj.ac.za

Consent

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to sign a separate consent form.